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First record of *Tephritis acanthiophilopsis* (Diptera: Tephritidae) from France

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Tephritis acanthiophilopsis Hering, 1938 is a fruit fly species (Tephritidae) primarily distributed throughout Central and Eastern Europe. Until recently, its known range included countries such as the Czech Republic, Hungary, Italy (mainland), Romania, Slovakia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004), The Netherlands (Smit & Aartsen, 2007), Germany, and Southern Russia (S. Korneyev, 2016).

Larvae of *T. acanthiophilopsis* are believed to feed in the flower heads of thistles (*Cirsium palustre* or other species occurring in the wet meadows), but the exact host plant remains unclear.

France has not been included in the species distribution list, and the record presented here is the first confirmed report of *T. acanthiophilopsis* in the country.

Material examined: France: Île-de-France, Hauts-de-Seine, Ville-d'Avray, Forêt de Fausses Reposes, a small forest clearing with long grass (48.8227 N, 2.1794 E), 12.11.2025, 1 ♀ (A. Dehalleux obs., not collected).

This record significantly extends the known western border of the *T. acanthiophilopsis* range and confirms its presence in Western Europe. The finding in November is also quite late for fruit flies and may indicate a long flight period or hibernation as adult of the species in this locality. (Figs 1–2).

Furthermore, an online observation suggests the presence of *T. acanthiophilopsis* in Belgium (<https://observations.be/observation/183979028/>) (Godfried Van Hertum obs.; Lieven Decrick det.). We verify this identification here.

Figs 1–2. *Tephritis acanthiophilopsis*, adult female: 1 — dorsally, 2 — laterally, shoing oviscape. Photo by A. Dehalleux.

References

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